

Web of Science

Tools Searches and alerts Search History Marked List

Select a database

Try our new Author Search^{BETA}

Basic Search Author Search^{BETA} Cited Reference Search **Advanced Search** Structure Search

Use field tags, Boolean operators, parentheses, and query sets to create your query. Results will appear in the Search History table at the bottom of the page. ([Learn more about Advanced Search](#))

Example: TS=(nanotub* AND carbon) NOT AU=Smalley RE #1 NOT #2 [more examples](#) | [view the tutorial](#)

Search

Restrict results by languages and document types:

All languages	All document types
English	Article
Afrikaans	Abstract of Published Item
Arabic	Art Exhibit Review

Timespan

Custom year range to

[More settings](#)

Booleans: AND, OR, NOT, SAME, NEAR

Field Tags:

TS= Topic	SA= Street Address
TI= Title	CI= City
AU= Author [Index]	PS= Province/State
AI= Author Identifiers	CU= Country/Region
GP= Group Author [Index]	ZP= Zip/Postal Code
ED= Editor	FO= Funding Agency
SO= Publication Name [Index]	FG= Grant Number
DO= DOI	FT= Funding Text
PY= Year Published	SU= Research Area
CF= Conference	WC= Web of Science Category
AD= Address	IS= ISSN/ISBN
OG= Organization-Enhanced [Index]	UT= Accession Number
OO= Organization	PMID= PubMed ID
SG= Suborganization	ALL= All Fields

Search History:

Set	Results	Save History / Create Alert	Open Saved History	Edit Sets	Combine Sets	Delete Sets
# 4	9,031 #2 AND #1 <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC Timespan=1999-2019</i>			Edit	☐ AND ☐ OR <input type="button" value="Combine"/>	<input type="button" value="Select All"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
# 3	9,468 #2 AND #1 <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC Timespan=All years</i>			Edit	☐	☐
# 2	192,141 TOPIC: (((step* OR stride*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*))) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR "single support" OR "double support") NEAR/2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*))) OR (((spatiotemporal OR "spatio-temporal") NEAR/2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*))) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR rhythm* OR volume* OR bout* OR duration* OR distance* OR intensit* OR variabilit* OR asymmetr* OR symmetr* OR parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic* OR assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR measure* OR test*))) <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC</i>			Edit	☐	☐

Timespan=All years

1 **476,615** **TOPIC:** (((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) NEAR/3 obstruct*) OR copd) OR (parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans") OR (((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) NEAR/3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat*) OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) NEAR/5 fracture*))
Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC
Timespan=All years

AND OR

Combine

Select All

Delete

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